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An Overview of the Substrates used in Microbial Fuel Cells

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a mini review on the substrates used in microbial fuel cells (MFCs) either for bioelectricity generation or simultaneous production of bioelectricity and resource recovery/waste treatment. Recent substrates that are being used for simultaneous production of bioelectricity and resource recovery as well as the key challenges for bioelectricity production in an MFC are also discussed. The paper expects to give an informative overview of the current development in the substrates used in MFCs, and to encourage more thinking and investigation towards further development of efficient processes for improved bioelectricity production and resource recovery in MFCs.

Keywords: Microbial Fuel Cells, Substrates, Bioelectricity, Power Density, Coulombic Efficiency.

List of abbreviations used

AUM	-	Artificial Urine Medium
BOD	-	Biological Oxygen Demand
MFC	-	Microbial Fuel Cell
PD	-	Power Density
CE	-	Coulombic Efficiency
CEM	-	Cation Exchange Membrane
CD	-	Current Density
COD	-	Chemical Oxygen Demand
CW	-	Constructed Wetlands
DAF	-	Dissolved Air Flotation
OCV	-	Open Circuit Voltage
PEM	-	Proton Exchange Membrane
SCMFC	-	Single Chamber Microbial Fuel Cell
SCOD	-	Soluble Chemical Oxygen Demand
SMFC	-	Solid-phase Microbial Fuel Cell
TCOD	-	Total Chemical Oxygen Demand
TOC	-	Total Organic Carbon

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustained innovations and continuous development efforts have been made by researchers for the development of alternative energy generation through renewable energy sources (Parikka, 2004; Dresselhaus and Thomas, 2001). In recent years, one of the most promising advances in renewable energy generation is microbial fuel cell (MFC) due to its possibility of directly harvesting electricity from organic wastes and renewable biomass (Lovley, 2006). Compared to other bioenergy technologies, MFCs offer the advantages of energy production directly from a substrate, high efficiency at room temperature, reliable base load power, waste treatment and low pollution impact (Kumar *et al.*, 2015). MFCs are devices that have the ability to produce bioelectricity from organic waste by means of microorganisms as biocatalysts. They operate under very mild conditions and use a wide range of biodegradable

materials as fuel. One of the advantages of MFCs is their capability to directly extract electric energy from organic matters in wastewater. MFCs can use microorganisms, primarily bacteria to transform the chemical energy of organic matter contained in wastewater into electricity. Thus, bioelectricity generation and simultaneous waste treatment may take place in a cell (Patil *et al.*, 2009).

Waste treatment is usually energy and cost intensive. However, it has been estimated that municipal wastewater contains approximately 9.3 times more energy than currently needed for its treatment in a modern municipal wastewater treatment plant (Li *et al.*, 2014). Although energy loss is unavoidable and could be considerable in MFC, theoretically it is possible to turn wastewater treatment into a self-sufficient or even a net energy-producing process. Based on the state-of-the-art practice for domestic wastewater treatment, it is estimated that an MFC would only consume 0.024 kW or 0.076 kWh/kg– chemical oxygen demand (COD) in average, which is about one order of magnitude less than activated sludge-based aerobic processes (0.3 kW or 0.6 kWh/kg - COD). Therefore, a positive energy balance in domestic wastewater treatment is theoretically achievable by MFCs alone on a liter scale.

MFC technology promises direct production of electricity in waste treatment. Table 1 depicts the electricity generation performance of a liter-scale MFCs for wastewater treatment. Moreover, it has been reported that MFCs could produce normalized energy recovery (NER) of 0.026 kWh/m³ wastewater, or 0.080 kWh/kg COD from municipal wastewater.

Table 1: Electricity generation performance of liter-scale MFCs for wastewater treatment

Wastewater	Reactor volume (L)	Max. PD (W/m ³)	NER (kWh/kg COD)	CE (%)
Municipal	20	0.17	0.003	0.3
Brewery	10	4.1	0.10	7.6
Synthetic	1.5	3.5	—	5

Various researchers have established the usefulness of MFCs towards many specialized and value-added applications beyond electricity generation, such as waste treatment and recovery of pure materials, the removal of organic matters, treatment of specific pollutants, bioremediation, heavy metal recovery, nitrification and denitrification, dye decolorization, water softening, bioproduction and related aspects, biomethane production, phosphorus recovery, production biohydrogen, biomass production, acetic acid production, and production of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), powering small portable electronic elements in remote locations, and implantable body devices (Mathuriya and Yakhmi, 2016; Choi, 2015).

In 2010, Pant *et al.*, (2010) conducted a comprehensive review of different substrates used in MFCs. The review summarizes the various substrates that have been used in MFCs for current production as well as waste treatment. However, since then a comprehensive review on the various substrates, which have been used and can possibly be used in MFCs is still lacking. In this article, we have reviewed all the substrates that have been used in MFCs so far. This paper provides a mini review on the substrates used in MFCs either for bioelectricity generation or simultaneous production of bioelectricity and resource recovery/waste treatment. Recent substrates that are being used for simultaneous production of bioelectricity and resource recovery as well as the key challenges for bioelectricity production in an MFC are also discussed.

2. MICROBIAL FUEL CELL TECHNOLOGY

2.1 Operating principles of an MFC

A typical MFC consists of two chambers: anodic and cathodic chambers partitioned by a proton exchange membrane (PEM) or salt bridge (Fig. 1). The anodic electron transfer mechanism in MFC is fundamental to understanding the theory of how MFCs work. The bacteria in the anode oxidize organic substrates such as glucose and acetate, and electrons and protons are generated as a result of microbial metabolism producing carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water (H₂O) as an oxidative by-product. The electrons produced flow to the cathode through an external circuit and protons cross a separator, usually a PEM or salt bridge. At the cathode, after crossing the PEM or salt bridge, the protons combine with atmospheric oxygen (O₂) to form H₂O. Thus, the cathodic reaction has a major impact on MFC performance. Microbes in the anodic chamber generate electrons (e⁻) and protons (H⁺) in the dissimilative process of oxidizing organic substrates (Logan and Regan, 2006). In MFCs, electricity generation is made possible by keeping the bacteria separated from oxygen or any other end terminal acceptor other than the anode in the anodic chamber Gezginci and Uysal (2016).

Fig. 1: Working principle and basic construction of MFC (Sonawane *et al.*, 2017)

2.2 Bacteria Used in MFCs

In the early 1900s, scientists showed that microbes (microscopic organisms, including bacteria) could make electricity, which is the basis of MFC technology. In 1911, bioelectricity generation from bacteria was first reported. Later in the beginning of the 1990s researchers have focused their attention on design and performance of MFCs. Similarly, during the last decades, significant advances have been made in terms of new materials, designs, low cost substrates that have reduced the final price of MFCs and increased their efficiency.

A wide range of bacteria possesses the ability to degrade organic substrate and transfer the electrons derived from the metabolism from anode to the cathode. Some of these bacteria used in MFCs and their substrates are listed in Table 2. Marine sediment (Xu *et al.*, 2017), soil (Niessen *et al.*, 2006), wastewater (Du *et al.*, 2007), fresh water sediment (Zhang *et al.*, 2006) and activated sludge are all rich sources of bacteria.

Table 2: Microbes used in MFCs (Du *et al.*, 2007)

Microbes	Substrates
<i>Actinobacillus succinogenes</i>	Glucose
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	Acetate
<i>Alcaligenes faecalis</i> , <i>Enterococcus gallinarum</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Glucose
<i>Clostridium beijerinckii</i>	Starch, glucose, lactate, molasses
<i>Clostridium butyricum</i>	Starch, glucose, lactate, molasses
<i>Desulfovibrio desulfuricans</i>	Sucrose
<i>Erwinia dissolven</i>	Glucose
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Glucose, sucrose
<i>Geobacter sulfurreducens</i>	Acetate
<i>Geobacter metallireducens</i>	Acetate
<i>Gluconobacter oxydans</i>	Glucose
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Glucose
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Glucose
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	Glucose
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Glucose
<i>Rhodospirillum rubrum</i>	Glucose, xylose, sucrose, maltose
<i>Shewanella oneidensis</i>	Lactate
<i>Shewanella putrefaciens</i>	Lactate, pyruvate, acetate, glucose
<i>Streptococcus lactis</i>	Glucose

2.3 Classification of MFC

MFCs can be classified into two types namely: mediator and mediator-less microbial fuel cells (Nielsen *et al.*, 2009; Gil *et al.*, 2003; Kim *et al.*, 2002; Park and Zeikus, 2000). In MFCs, electrons can be transferred to the cathode by electron mediators or shuttles (Rabaey *et al.*, 2004; Rabaey *et al.*, 2005), by direct membrane associated electron transfer (Bond and Lovley, 2003). Chemical mediators, such as neutral red or anthraquinone-2, 6-disulfonate (AQDS), can be added to the system to allow electricity production by the bacteria (Bond *et al.*, 2002).

2.4 Parameters Affecting MFCs Performance

The application and performance of MFC as an alternative energy option have attracted growing research interest in recent times (e.g., Xu *et al.*, 2017; Niessen *et al.*, 2006; Du *et al.*, 2007; Zhang *et al.*, 2006). However, low power output and current density (CD) are some of the key factors affecting bioelectricity generation in MFCs (Rahimnejad *et al.*, 2015).

Though, there is limited information about the factors that affect the power output of MFCs using soil organic matter, sewage sludge, marine sediment, garden compost, urine, industrial and domestic waste and animal waste as fuel source, a large number of factors such as substrate (feedstock), temperature, MFC configuration, type and size of electrodes have been reported to have limiting impact on the performance of MFCs (Shantaram *et al.*, 2005).

In 2009, Balat (2009) reported that the performance of a MFC could be influenced by several factors such as the current, power density (PD), and rate of fuel oxidation. The authors also reported that various factors such as anodic catalytic activity, fuel diffusion, and the diffusion and consumption of electrons and protons could also influence the rate of fuel oxidation in MFCs.

Furthermore, Zhou *et al.*, (2013) analysed MFC operating principles using bioenergetics and bioelectrochemistry. Results showed that despite major advances in the past decade, further improvements in MFC power output such as the use of catalytic materials for MFC electrodes are needed to improve the MFC performance. According to Ahn *et al.*, (2014), depending on the goal of the experiment – either for power generation or treating domestic wastewater, different electrode configurations have been found to affect the performance of multielectrode MFCs. Similarly, different parts of MFC such as anode, cathode and membrane have been shown to affect the performance of MFCs. For example, Rahimnejad *et al.*, (2015) reported that low power output MFCs can be solved by increasing the surface area of the electrodes as well as the use of a suitable power management program: the data are transferred only when enough energy is stored by using ultra capacitor.

In MFCs, non-corrosive and carbon-based materials are usually used as anodes. In some cases, however, metals have been used that can corrode (e.g. copper) or that are corrosion resistant (e.g. stainless steel). Corrosion could increase current through galvanic (abiotic) current production or by increasing exposed surface area, or decrease current due to generation of toxic products from corrosion. In order to directly examine the effects of using corrodible metal anodes, MFCs with Cu were compared with reactors using stainless steel and carbon cloth anodes in a study conducted by Logan and Zhu (2014). Findings revealed that MFCs with Cu anodes initially showed high current generation similar to abiotic controls, but subsequently produced low power (2 mW/m²).

Nonetheless, among effective parameters on performance of MFCs, substrate type and concentrations have been shown to have a significant effect on the power output of the cell (Zhang *et al.*, 2001; Pant *et al.*, 2010; Nielsen *et al.*, 2009). Table 3 depicts the typical substrates and their reactions in the anode and cathode of MFCs.

Table 3: Typical substrates used in MFCs and their related reactions

Substrate	Anodic Reaction	Cathodic Reaction
Acetate	$\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- + 4\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{HCO}_3^- + 9\text{H}^+ + 8\text{e}^-$	$\text{O}_2 + 8\text{e}^- + 8\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Glucose	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 6\text{CO}_2 + 24\text{H}^+ + 24\text{e}^-$	$24\text{H}^+ + 24\text{e}^- + 6\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Butyrate	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2 + 4\text{H}^+ + 4\text{e}^-$	$\text{O}_2 + 4\text{e}^- + 4\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Glycerol	$\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_3 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 3\text{HCO}_3^- + 17\text{H}^+ + 14\text{e}^-$	$2\text{O}_2 + 14\text{e}^- + 14\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Malate	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{O}_5^- + 7\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 4\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3 + 11\text{H}^+ + 12\text{e}^-$	$3\text{O}_2 + 12\text{e}^- + 12\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Citrate	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7^{3-} + 11\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 6\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3 + 15\text{H}^+ + 18\text{e}^-$	$3\text{O}_2 + 18\text{e}^- + 18\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Acetate	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{CO}_2 + 8\text{H}^+ + 8\text{e}^-$	$2\text{O}_2 + 8\text{H}^+ + 8\text{e}^- \rightarrow 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

3. Substrates used in MFCs

Substrate otherwise referred to as anolyte refers to the liquid solution inside the anodic chamber. It is important for any biological process as it serves as carbon (nutrient) and energy source. It is a feedstock (substrate) for anodophilic

microorganisms, providing carbon-energy, electrons and nutrients including minerals, salts and amino acids. The efficiency and economic viability of converting organic wastes to bioenergy depend on the characteristics and components of the organic material. Substrate influences not only the integral composition of the bacterial community in the anode biofilm, but also the MFC performance (Chae *et al.*, 2009). In MFCs, substrate is regarded as one of the most important factors affecting electricity generation (Liu *et al.*, 2009). Anolyte (substrate type, concentration and feeding rate) as an electron donor is one of the most important biological factors affecting the structure, composition and affinity of the microbial community, which can subsequently influence the MFC performance in terms of power density and coulombic efficiency (Liu *et al.*, 2009; Chae *et al.*, 2009). Table 4 depicts some of the key parameters evaluating the MFC performance.

It was shown that, under normal condition, when there are no other limitations for the anodic biofilm to function, the relationship between substrate concentration and MFC current generation usually follows Monod's equation (Borole *et al.*, 2011). Thus, increasing substrate concentration results to higher power output up to a certain level (Chang & Kim, 2006). However, this is not always the case. Pinto *et al.* (2010) reported that a high organic load could promote methanogenic metabolism, rather than current production when the system is run under non-optimal conditions such as too high external load.

Table 4: Key parameters evaluating the MFC performance

Parameter	Unit	Calculation/measurement
Electrode potential	V	Measured between an electrode and a reference electrode
Open circuit voltage	V	OCV (V_{OC}), voltage at infinite resistance
Voltage	V	Measured between two ends under the applied external resistance (R_{EXT})
Current	A	$I = V/R$ R is the loaded external resistance value in ohms (Ω).
Power	W	$P = IV$ The maximum power (P_{MAX}) is calculated from the polarization curve.
Current density	A/m^2 A/m^3	$j = I/A$, $j = I/V$ A is total/projected anode/cathode surface area in square meters (m^2) and V is the total reactor/anodic chamber/cathodic chamber volume in cubic meters (m^3).
Power density	W/m^2 W/m^3	$PD = P/A$, $PD = P/V$ A and V are the same as above.
Coulombic efficiency	%	(For batch feed system) $CE_{batch} = \frac{M \int_0^t I dt}{FnV_{anodic} \Delta COD}$ M is the molecular weight of oxygen (32), F is Faraday's constant, n is the number of electrons exchanged per mole of oxygen, V_{anodic} is the volume of liquid in the anodic chamber, and ΔCOD is the change in COD over time t. (For continuous feed system) $CE_{cont} = \frac{MI}{FbQ\Delta COD}$ This is on the basis of current generated under steady condition. Q is the volumetric influent flow rate and ΔCOD is the difference in the influent and effluent COD.
Internal resistance	Ω	(From polarization curve) $P_{MAX} = VO/C^2 R_{EXT}/(R_{INT} + R_{EXT})^2$ Or $R_{INT} = (VO/C / I_L) - R_{EXT}$ I_L is the current under a load and R_{EXT} is the value of the applied resistance
Treatment efficiency	%	$\eta = \Delta C/C \times 100\%$ ΔC is removed substrate and C is the total substrate fed, this can be measured in BOD, COD (chemical oxygen demand) or TOC (total organic carbon).
Organic loading rate	$kg/m^3/day$	$OLR = COD \times V_{reactor} / V_{anodic}$ $V_{reactor}$ is the reactor volume.
Organic removal rate	$kg/m^3/day$	$ORR = \Delta COD \times V_{reactor} / V_{anodic}$
Hydraulic retention time	Hour	$HRT = V_{anodic} / V_{reactor}$

[1]

$$\mu = \mu_{\max} \frac{S}{K_s + S}$$

Where, μ is the specific growth rate of the microorganisms, μ_{\max} , is the maximum specific growth rate of the microorganisms, S , is the concentration of the limiting substrate for growth and K_s , is the half saturation constant.

High current output and flexible fuel utilization, including substrates of macromolecular nature, are prerequisites for a successful implementation of MFCs for bioenergy generation, resource recovery and waste treatment. MFCs have been used to generate bioelectricity from various organic compounds. A wide range of substrates from pure compounds to complex mixtures of organic matter has been used in MFC studies. Pant *et al.* (2010) reported that simple compounds such as acetate and butyrate are easier to degrade in MFCs thus tend to improve the power output whereas complex substrates are favored by diverse and electrochemically active bacterial communities. However various target compounds still need to be investigated in MFCs. For example, human urine, which showed a great potential in terms of power generation and sanitation improvement (Ieropoulos, Greenman & Melhuish, 2012), has not been much explored. A comprehensive list of substrates that have been used in MFC including type of inoculum used and current output is presented in Table 5.

Unlike in the previous years where simple substrates such as, mannoses, acetate and glucose were commonly used in MFCs, in recent years, a variety of unconventional substrates such as wastewater and urine are being used by researchers with the aim of treating wastewater, resource recovery and improving MFC output at the same time (Chouler *et al.*, 2016; Ieropoulos *et al.*, 2013). Some of the most common substrates and their influence on MFC performance are discussed below. In this paper, substrates used in MFCs are classified into: Conventional substrates - those that have been used in the early stages of the MFCs) and unconventional substrates - those that have been used recently for bioelectricity production and resource recovery.

Table 5: Substrates used in MFCs (Pant *et al.*, 2010)

Type of Substrate	Concentration	Inoculum Source	Current density (mAcm ⁻²) at Maximum Power
Acetate	1 g/L	Pre-acclimated bacteria from MFC	0.8
Arabitol	1220 mg/L	Pre-acclimated bacteria from MFC	0.68
Azo dye with glucose	300 mg/L	Mixture of aerobic and anaerobic sludge	0.09
Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC)	1 g/L	Co-culture of <i>Clostridium cellulolyticum</i> and <i>G. sulfurreducens</i>	0.05
Cellulose particles	4 g/L	Pure culture of <i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	0.02
Corn stover biomass	1 g/L COD	Domestic wastewater	0.15
Cysteine	385 mg/L	Sediment sample from 30 cm depth	0.0186
1,2-Dichloroethane	99 mg/L	Microbial consortia from acetate enriched MFC	0.008
Ethanol	10 mM	Anaerobic sludge from wastewater plant	0.025
Farm manure	3 kg in water (20% w/v)	Self build up of anaerobic environment	0.004
Furfural	6.8 mM	Pre-acclimated bacteria from anode of a ferricyanide-cathode MFC	0.17
Galactitol	1220 mg/L	Pre-acclimated bacteria from MFC	0.78
Glucose	6.7 mM	Mixed bacterial culture maintained on sodium acetate for 1 year (<i>Rhodococcus</i> and <i>Paracoccus</i>)	0.70
Glucuronic acid	6.7 mM	Mixed bacterial culture	1.18
Lactate	18 mM	Pure culture of <i>S. oneidensis</i> MR-1	0.005
Landfill leachate	6000 mg/L	Leachate and sludge	0.0004
Macroalgae, <i>Ulva lactuca</i>	2500 mg/L COD	Primary clarifier overflow of wastewater plant	0.25
Malt extract, yeast extract and glucose	1%	Pure culture of <i>E. cloacae</i>	0.067

Mannitol	1220 mg/L	Pre-acclimated bacteria from MFC	0.58
Microalgae: <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	2500 mg/L COD	Primary clarifier overflow of wastewater plant	0.20
Microcrystalline cellulose	7.5 g/L	Rumen microorganism from rumen of a cow	0.02
Nitilotriacetic acid (NTA)	48.5 mg/L	Oligotrophic consortium enriched with river water	0.0005
Phenol	400 mg/L	Mixed aerobic activated sludge and anaerobic sludge (1:1, v/v)	0.1
Propionate	0.53 mM	Anaerobic sludge	0.035
Ribitol	1220 mg/L	Pre-acclimated bacteria from MFC	0.73
Sodium formate	20 mM	Anaerobic digested fluid from a sewage treatment plant	0.22
Sodium fumarate	25 mM	Pure culture of <i>G. sulfurreducens</i>	2.05
Sorbitol	1220 mg/L	Pre-acclimated bacteria from MFC	0.62
Starch	10 g/L	Pure culture of <i>Clostridium butyricum</i>	1.3
Sucrose	2674 mg/L	Anaerobic sludge from septic tank	0.19
Xylitol	1220 mg/L	Pre-acclimated bacteria from MFC	0.71
Xylose	6.7 mM	Mixed bacterial culture	0.74
Xylose and humic acid	10 mM	Domestic wastewater	0.06
Wastewaters			
Artificial wastewater with glucose and glutamate	300 mg/L	Anaerobic sludge	0.02
Brewery wastewater	2240 mg/L	Full strength brewery wastewater	0.2
Beer brewery wastewater	600 mg/L	Anaerobic mixed consortia	0.18
Chocolate industry wastewater	1459 mg/L COD	Activated sludge	0.302
Domestic wastewater	600 mg/L	Anaerobic sludge	0.06
Food processing wastewater	1672 mg/L COD	Anaerobic sludge	0.05
Meat processing wastewater	1420 mg/L	Domestic wastewater	0.115
Paper recycling wastewater	2.452 g/L	Diluted paper recycling wastewater	0.25
Protein-rich wastewater	1.75 g/L COD	Mesophilic anaerobic sludge	0.008
Real urban wastewater	330 mg/L	Domestic wastewater	0.018
Starch processing wastewater	4852 mg/L COD	Starch processing wastewater	0.09
Swine wastewater	8320 mg/L COD	Full-strength swine wastewater	0.015
Synthetic acid-mine drainage water	0.007 M Fe ²⁺	Medium with NaCl and NaHCO ₃ sparged with N ₂ and CO ₂	0.064
Synthetic wastewater	12.1 g/L COD	Anaerobic mixed consortia producing hydrogen	0.086
Synthetic wastewater	16 g COD/day	Granular sludge from a upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactor	0.017
Synthetic wastewater	510 mg/L	Anaerobic culture from a preexisting MFC	0.008
Synthetic wastewater with molasses and urea	1000 mg/L	Anaerobic mixture from wastewater plant	0.005
Wastewater amended with acetate	1600 mg/L	Domestic wastewater	0.08

3.1 Conventional Substrates

Various organics can be utilized in MFCs for bioelectricity generation. Major metabolic fuels – carbohydrates, fatty acids and amino acids are the monomers of all complex and high molecular weight compounds. Of all these organics, carbohydrates are by far the most abundant group. Simple (fermentable) substrates such as acetate have been reported to result in more electricity generation than complex (unfermentable) ones, because of relatively simpler degradation pathways that could have less energy loss, which is demonstrated well in power production (power output). Acetate (Bond *et al.*, 2002; Liu *et al.*, 2005; Chae *et al.*, 2009) and glucose (Kim *et al.*, 2000; Rabaey *et al.*, 2003) are the most commonly used substrate in MFCs.

However, acetate, which is the most widely used substrate in MFC research, (Liu *et al.*, 2005) has been shown to produce higher PD than glucose ($p < 0.03$), sucrose ($p < 0.01$), or actual wastewaters ($p < 0.01$) that are more complex (Ge *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, in terms of energy recovery, acetate still exhibits a better performance than actual wastewaters ($p < 0.05$), while the NERs from glucose are statistically similar to those from wastewater ($p > 0.05$) (Ge *et al.*, 2014).

In 2004, Niessen *et al.* (2004) demonstrated that by combining specially designed anodes, consisting of platinum covered by polytetrafluoroaniline and living cells of the biocatalyst *Clostridium butyricum* or *Clostridium beijerinckii* bioelectricity can be generated from a variety of substrates, including starch, one of the major biomass constituents. Findings revealed that current densities between 1 and 1.3 mA/cm² could be achieved by using glucose, molasses, or starch as substrates.

Rabaey *et al.* (2003) investigated the power output of an MFC in relation to glucose dosage containing a mixed bacterial culture utilizing glucose as carbon source. Results revealed that electron recovery in terms of bioelectricity up to 89% occurred for glucose feeding rates in the range 0.5–3 g/L/d, at powers up to 3.6 W/m² of electrode surface.

Bioelectricity production from acetate, glucose and xylose with humic acid as a mediator in a two chamber MFC was investigated by Thygesen *et al.* (2008). Results revealed that acetate produced the highest voltage (570 mV) and maximum PD ($PD_{max} = 123 \text{ mW/m}^2$) due to a simpler metabolism than with glucose and xylose. Glucose and xylose resulted in PD_{max} of 28 mW/m² and 32 mW/m² at lower voltage of 380 mV and 414 mV, respectively. PD_{max} increased by 84% and 30%, for glucose and xylose respectively, when humic acid (2 g L⁻¹) was present in the medium. The increase of PD_{max} due to humic acid presence was attributed to its ability to act as mediator. It was also found that even though pH decreased to 5 with glucose and xylose, due to production of acetate and propionate, the voltage remained on the same level of 250–350 mV.

In MFCs bioelectricity generation could be sustained over a cycle primarily by stored substrate and intermediates formed by fermentation. Huang and Logan (2008) developed a medium-scale (0.77 L) air-cathode; brush anode MFC, which was operated in fed-batch mode using xylose (20 mM). Findings revealed that xylose (20 mM) generated a maximum power density of $13 \pm 1 \text{ W/m}^3$ ($673 \pm 43 \text{ mW/m}^2$). It was also found that xylose was rapidly removed (83.5%) within 8 h of a 60-h cycle, with 42.1% of electrons in intermediates (8.5 \pm 0.2 mM acetate, 5.9 \pm 0.01 mM ethanol, 4.3 \pm 0.1 mM formate, and 1.3 \pm 0.03 mM propionate), 9.1% captured as electricity, 16.1% in the remaining xylose, and 32.7% lost to cell storage, biomass, and other processes. The final CE was found to be 50%. Furthermore, at a higher initial xylose concentration (54 mM), xylose was again rapidly removed (86.9% within 24 h of a 116-h cycle), intermediates increased in concentration (18.4 \pm 0.4 mM acetate, 7.8 \pm 0.4 mM ethanol and 2.1 \pm 0.2 mM propionate), but power was lower (5.2 \pm 0.4 W/m³). Operating the reactor in continuous flow mode at a hydraulic retention time of 20 h increased the power of the MFC (20 \pm 1 W/m³), with 66 \pm 1% chemical oxygen demand removal.

The effect of fructose concentrations on power output and current density of a dual chamber microbial fuel cell was investigated by Jafary *et al.* (2011). A wide range of fructose concentrations of 10, 20, 30 and 40 g/L were used in the study using *S. cerevisiae* as the biocatalyst, 100 μ m of neutral red as mediator and also 100 μ m ferricyanide as oxidizer at the anode and cathode chambers, respectively. Results showed that substrate concentration with 10 g/L of fructose demonstrated the maximum power and optimum current density of 32.16 mW/m² and 96.59 mA/m², respectively.

Bioelectricity generation in a single chambered MFC using acetate and butyrate as substrates was investigated by Liu *et al.* (2005). Results demonstrated that power generated with acetate (800 mg/L) (506 mW/m² or 12.7 mW/L) was up to 66% higher than that fed with butyrate (1000 mg/L) (305 mW/m² or 7.6 mW/L), demonstrating that acetate is a preferred aqueous substrate for electricity generation in MFCs. However, CEs and overall energy recovery were 10-31 and 3-7% for acetate and 8-15 and 2-5% for butyrate, indicating substantial electron and energy losses to the processes other than electricity generation.

In 2012, Mokhtarian *et al.* (2012) examined the maximum open circuit voltage; highest power output; and current density in a MFC using palm oil mill effluent anaerobic sludge as active biocatalyst. Glucose, sucrose, fructose and molasses were individually implemented as substrate for bioelectricity production in the MFC. Results

revealed that maximum bioelectricity generation was obtained from molasses as substrate. The maximum power output and current generated were 55.25 mW/m² and 208.55 mA/m², respectively.

3.2 Unconventional Substrates

In recent years, attention has shifted to the use of unconventional substrates such as human urine, industrial wastewater, plant waste, and swine waste for MFCs research (Edem *et al.*, 2015) in addition to the aforementioned conventional ones. These are discussed in the following sub-sections.

3.2.1 Human Neat urine

Urine is an abundant waste product, which requires energy intensive treatment processes in modern wastewater treatment plants. However urine can be utilised as fertiliser in the form of struvite and/or bioenergy generation in MFCs. Huge volumes of urine are being produced worldwide. Thus, urine could be used to revolutionize the way we produce bioelectricity by harnessing the potential power of the urine using MFCs.

Urine pretreatment has attracted increasing interest, as it is able to relieve the nitrogen and phosphorus overloading problems in municipal wastewater treatment plants as well as bioelectricity generation. For instance, recently in 2016, a 3-stage MFC/struvite extraction process system was developed and tested by You *et al.* (2016) in order to maximise urine utilisation in terms of electricity generation and struvite recovery. Results indicated that in the first stage, while generating electrical energy, MFCs accelerated urea hydrolysis, which was beneficial for the struvite precipitation process in the following stage. The authors also tested power generation and more efficient COD reduction after collecting struvite by adding magnesium into the initial effluent, and using the supernatant. In total, 82% of PO₄³⁻-P and 20% of COD of undiluted human urine were removed by the 3-stage system. Also 14.32 W/m³ (absolute power: 358 μW) and 11.76 W/m³ (absolute power: 294 μW) of power were produced from the 1st and 3rd stages of the system, respectively, during operation.

Chouler *et al.* (2016) investigated the development of an effective small-scale MFC for energy generation from urine. The authors used an innovative air-cathode miniature MFC and the effect of electrode length was also investigated. The researchers also investigated the impacts of two different biomass derived catalysts. Results showed that doubling the electrode length resulted in the power density increasing by one order of magnitude (from 0.053 to 0.580 W/m³). It was also found that when three devices were electrically connected in parallel, the power output was over 10 times higher compared to individual units and the use of biomass-derived oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) catalysts at the cathode increased the power density generated by the MFC up to 1.95 W/m³.

In 2012, Kuntke *et al.* (2012) proved that ammonium recovery and energy production could be achieved simultaneously from urine. The authors developed a MFC that simultaneously produce energy and recover ammonium using a gas diffusion cathode. Findings showed that the ammonium transport to the cathode occurred due to migration of ammonium and diffusion of ammonia and ionic ammonium was converted to volatile ammonia due to the high pH. Ammonia was recovered from the liquid-gas boundary via volatilization and subsequent absorption into an acid solution. The authors further found that an ammonium recovery rate of 3.29 gN/d/m² (vs. membrane surface area) could be achieved at a current density of 0.50 A/m² (vs. membrane surface area) and the energy balance showed an energy surplus of 3.46 kJ/g_N, which means more energy was produced than needed for the ammonium recovery.

Santoro *et al.*, (2013) also investigated the potential of single chamber microbial fuel cells (SCMFC) to treat raw, fresh human urine for power generation, COD removal, and nutrient recovery using platinum (Pt)-based cathode. Results showed that the power generation (55 μW) of the SCMFCs with platinum (Pt)-based cathode was higher than those with Pt-free cathodes (23 μW) at the beginning of the tests, but this difference decreased over time. They also found that up to 75% of the chemical oxygen demand (COD) in urine was reduced after a 4-day treatment. It was also found that the ammonium concentration increased significantly to 5 gNH₄⁺-N/L in SCMFCs due to urea hydrolysis, while sulfate concentration decreased and transformed into H₂S due to sulfate reduction reactions. However, calcium and magnesium concentrations dropped due to precipitation at high pH, and phosphorous decreased to 20–50% due to the formation of struvite that was found on the cathode surface and on the bottom of the anodic chamber.

In 2013, Ieropoulos *et al.* (2013a) demonstrated the feasibility of using human neat urine as a substrate in MFC. The authors demonstrated that neat undiluted urine could be utilised as the main feedstock for different types of individual MFCs and stacks of small-scale MFCs, for direct electricity production, with conversion efficiencies of >50%. Results showed that the smallest MFC (1.4 mL total volume) produced equal amounts of power to that produced by larger MFCs (6.25 mL), resulting in increased power densities. Power densities of 4.93 mW/m² (absolute power of 1.5 mW) were recorded when 48 small-scale MFCs were connected as a stack and fed with urine.

Similarly, in 2013, Ieropoulos *et al.* (2013b) for the first time reported the possibility of using a membrane-less MFCs fed with real neat urine to charge a commercially mobile phone. The authors demonstrated that a stack of MFCs feeding on urine could directly charge mobile phone batteries. Findings revealed that compared to other commonplace organic feedstocks, urine is shown to be a superior fuel for direct electricity generation.

Furthermore, Santoro *et al.* (2013) investigated a novel treatment process for human urine in membrane less single-chamber microbial fuel cells (SCMFCs). They authors tested the performances of SCMFCs with Pt-based or Pt-free cathode for over 1000 hours of operation. They observed that the pH of the anodic solution increased from 5.4–6.4 to 9.0 due to the urea hydrolysis, which consequently decreased the anodic performance even though the cathode was not affected, indicating that the MFCs were anode-limited. It was also observed that the solution conductivity increased up to 3 times the initial value. Results further showed that the initial current generated by the Pt-free cathodes SCMFCs was 0.13–0.15 mA, which stabilized at 0.1 mA. The Pt-based cathode SCMFC decreased from 0.18–0.23 mA to 0.13 mA.

3.2.2 Synthetic urine

Simple artificial (synthetic) urine medium (AUM), which provides conditions similar to that found in human neat urine has been reported to be a suitable replacement for normal human urine for use in a wide range of experiments (Brooks and Keevil, 1997). For example, Chouler *et al.* (2016) investigated the development of an effective small-scale air-cathode miniature MFC for energy generation using artificial urine medium (AUM) as the feedstock.

3.2.3 Microalgae

Microalgae, a diverse group of prokaryotic and eukaryotic photosynthetic microorganisms are microscopic photosynthetic organisms that usually grow in aquatic environments. They are composed of unicellular or simple multicellular structure that allows them to grow rapidly and live in extreme conditions. Microalgae are capable of harnessing solar energy quickly and efficiently through photosynthesis process to produce oils or sugars in a more efficient manner than crop plants. Microalgae are commonly used as substrate for the production of biodiesel.

Based on the pigmentation of their biological structure, microalgae can be grouped into different categories i) green algae (*Chlorophyta*), red algae (*Rhodophyta*) and diatoms (*Bacillariophyta*). Based on their mode of feeding, they can also be classified into two groups: i) autotrophic, which only require inorganic compounds to grow, such as CO₂, salts (nitrate ion, phosphate) and light, and ii) heterotrophs, which use sunlight or organic compounds as source of energy. The ability of microalgae to fix atmospheric CO₂ would help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and can be used to treat wastewater and generate many types of high value added products, and their use in MFCs being one of the most promising applications, which allows electricity production and CO₂ capture simultaneously. They can be used in the anode, as substrate, or in the cathode to produce oxygen and fix carbon dioxide.

During the light phase, microalgae carry out the production of electrons and protons in the anodic chamber. The organism uses CO₂ and light to perform photosynthesis to synthesize organic substrates; algal biomass and oxygen. At the anode, anodic microorganisms degrade algae wastes and excreted solutes, producing electrons and protons. The oxygen produced during the light period is consumed by microalgae in the dark phase. In this stage, organic substrates generated during the photosynthesis process are oxidized to obtain energy. Although microalgae have been proven as substrate for exoelectrogenic bacteria in the anodic chamber of MFCs, fresh microalgal biomass does not always produce a sufficiently high power density (Baicha *et al.*, 2016).

During the last decade, many research works have focused on using microalgae in MFCs for bioelectricity generation. A comprehensive review of the current MFCs technologies based on microalgae as substrate for bioelectricity production was conducted by Baicha *et al.* (2016). The authors also discussed the advantages, limitations and future prospects of the technologies. Table 6 shows the most common species of microalgae used in biotechnology, their biomass production, the type of culture medium they require and the operation mode.

Table 6: Bioelectricity generation and COD removal by different microalgal strains (Baicha et al., 2016)

Microalgae used in the anode							
Microalgal strains	MFC type	Anode	Cathode	Max. power density (mW/m²)	COD removal (%)	OCV (V)	Operating time (h)
<i>Scenedesmus obliquus</i>	Double chamber	Toray carbon paper	Toray carbon paper	102	74	-	150
<i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	Double chamber	Graphite rod	Graphite rod	30.15	-	-	-
<i>Spirulina platensis</i>	Double chamber	Platinum electrodes	Platinum electrodes	6.5	-	0.24	12
<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Duran bottle + beaker	Gold mesh	Carbon cloth	10	-	0.49	168
	Single chamber	Graphite felt	Carbon cloth-coated Pt	78	-	-	96
<i>Arthrospira axima (Spirulina maxima)</i>	Double chamber	Graphite	Graphite	20.5	67	-	1920
<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii transformation F5</i>	Double chamber	Graphite electrodes	Graphite electrodes	12.947	-	0.215	24
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Double chamber	Graphite brushes	Graphite brushes	13	73 ± 3	-	336
	Double chamber	Graphite plate	Graphite plate	15	18.4	-	480
	Single chamber	Graphite fiber brush	Carbon cloth-coated Pt	980	79.6	-	144
<i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i>	Double chamber	Graphite plate electrodes	Graphite plate electrodes	5.3	16.8	-	480
Microalgae used in the cathode							
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Double chamber	Glassy graphite rods	Glassy graphite rods	2.7	-	-	130
	Double chamber	Carbon felt	Carbon fiber cloth	8.79	84.8	-	400
	Single chamber + sediment	Graphite felt	Multi-walled carbon nanotubes	38	-	-	288
	Double chamber	Toray carbon cloth	Toray carbon cloth	13.5	80	0.49	600
	Modified MFC + tubular photobioreactor	Carbon felt	Carbon paper-coated Pt	27.5	-	-	432
	Double chamber	Carbon fiber brush	Carbon cloth	19.45	-	0.8	200
	Double chamber	Carbon fiber	Carbon cloth	1926 ± 21.4	90	-	480

		brush					
	Double chamber	Plain graphite	Plain graphite	62.7	-	-	264
	Double chamber	Toray carbon cloth	Toray carbon cloth	23.97	75	0.43	-
	Double chamber	carbon Plain paper	Carbon fiber brush	30	-	0.52	1008
<i>Scenedesmus obliquus</i>	Double chamber	Plain carbon paper	Carbon paper-coated Pt	154	-	-	192
<i>Desmodesmus sp. A8</i>	Double chamber	Plain graphite felt	Plain graphite felt	99.09	-	-	140

3.2.4 Wastewater

A large amount of organic high strength wastewater are produced by food processing, breweries, and pharmaceutical industries causing serious environmental problems, thus requiring a treatment before their release in the environment. One of the serious environmental problems is the ammonium pollution related to nitrogen-rich effluents.

In recent years, there have been substantial improvement and technological advancement in the MFC processes on waste/wastewater treatments (Ge *et al.* 2014). The effectiveness of carbon and ammonium removal in H-type mediator-less MFC was investigated by Bavasso *et al.* (2016) using an anaerobic digestion residue as a source of microorganisms. The authors evaluated the performances of an H-type MFC in term of organic carbon and ammonium nitrogen removal. Synthetic wastewaters, with different total organic carbon (TOC)/N ratios, were tested in their research. Results revealed that carbon reduction (up to 78%) resulted to be enhanced by values of TOC vs. N ratio higher than 1, while a high ammonium reduction (up to 70%) was obtained when the TOC vs. N ratio was lower than 1. In the latter case, the cation exchange membrane (CEM) supported nitrite accumulation, that is the first step of ammonium conversion into molecular nitrogen (N₂), by ensuring the optimal value of OD in anodic chamber.

Although Zhang *et al.* (2016) first argues that the MFC is not a suitable energy source for industrial and household use due high power output requirement and that MFC technology should be applied as a waste/wastewater treatment unit rather than a renewable energy source, Pandey *et al.* (2016), in extensive review of existing literature, reported that substrates rich in mixture of carbon sources (e.g., glucuronic acid, galactitol, ribitol, xylose, glucose, galactose, gluconic acid, xylitol, and arabitol); nitrogen sources (e.g., serine, histidine, and arginine); and organic acids (e.g., acetic acid, and lactic acid) have been proven to show a better performance in terms of power output. The authors further explained that ethanol stillage, cassava mill, chocolate industry, molasses, biodiesel, wastewaters have shown efficient capacity for bioelectricity production. Because huge amounts of agricultural, brewery, domestic, and food wastewaters are generated throughout the world, they offer potential feedstocks for fueling MFCs.

Among these, distillery industry along with agro processing industry wastewaters have better efficiency because of presence of methanogenic inhibitors and natural presence of electron transferring mediators like lignin in them. Thus substrates derived from lignocellulosic biomass and hydrolysates seem to be good choice as feed for MFCs. Food and dairy industry wastewaters are also represent good substrates for MFCs. However, the presence of other electron acceptors and of non-exoelectrogenic microorganisms such as fermenters limits their application. Animal processing industry associated wastewaters particularly from slaughterhouse and swine yards have good efficacy because of the presence of blood, which is a good substrate for microorganisms, as a major constituent in these wastes.

Nevertheless, MFCs possess a great potential to bring about innovation and become a promising avenue for wastewater treatment, resource and energy recovery (Zhang and Angelidaki, 2011; You, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2011). Integrating MFCs into constructed wetlands (CWs) has been proposed to eliminate the need and cost of building a reactor, while CWs provide the simultaneous redox conditions required for optimum MFC performance. A two-stage MFC-CW system was run by Doherty and Zhao (2015) for fuller wastewater treatment and increased power production. The results indicate that a two-stage MFC-CW can increase the normalized energy recovery and improve removal efficiencies of COD, total nitrogen, NH₄⁺, total phosphorus and reactive phosphorus to 93 ± 1.7%, 85 ± 5.2%, 90 ± 5.4%, 98 ± 5.3% and 99 ± 2.9%, respectively.

To improve the voltage output of MFC from lake sediment, Zhang and Angelidaki (2012) developed an innovative self-stacked submersible MFC that successfully produced a maximum power density of 294 mWm^{-2} and had an open circuit voltage (OCV) of 1.12 V. Voltage reversal, in terms of its cause, determining parameters and elimination method was also investigated by the authors. Findings revealed that the internal resistance and OCV were the most important parameters for predicting voltage reversal and the use of a capacitor was found to be an effective way to prevent voltage reversal and at the same time store power.

3.2.5 Lignocellulosic biomass, cellulose and chitin

Cellulose and chitin particulate substrates are cheap and readily available biopolymeric materials that can be used for bioelectricity generation in MFCs. Cellulosic materials are particularly attractive as a sustainable source of fuels and materials because of their relatively low cost and plentiful supply. Microbial cellulose utilization is responsible for one of the largest material flows in the biosphere and is of interest in relation to analysis of carbon flux at both local and global scales. The importance of microbial cellulose utilization in natural environments is further enhanced by the status of ruminants as a major source of dietary protein. Microbial cellulose utilization is also an integral component of widely used processes such as MFC technology for overcoming the recalcitrance of cellulosic biomass.

Cellulosic biomass, in the form of lignocellulosic materials, is a promising source of organic substrate for MFCs. It can be used as electron donor source in MFC for direct electricity production using exoelectrogenic bacteria. In 2005, Niessen *et al.* (2005) first demonstrated that insoluble cellulose could be used as substrate for electricity generation in MFCs. Though pretreatment of the cellulosic biomass is essential to convert cellulose and hemicellulose in the lignocellulosic biomass to soluble sugars (hydrolysates), which are used for bioelectricity generation, Hassan *et al.* (2012) have demonstrated that mixed and pure cultures of cellulose-degrading bacteria are capable of producing electricity directly from cellulose as the electron donor without pretreatment, and electron transfer to an anode electrode without supplying the MFC with external electron mediators.

Research findings have shown that lignocellulosic biomass derived monosaccharides are also a suitable resource for bioelectricity generation using MFC technology. Direct generation of electricity from monosaccharides (six hexoses (d-glucose, d-galactose, d(-)-levulose (fructose), l-fucose, l-rhamnose, and d-mannose), three pentoses (d-xylose, d(-)-arabinose, and d(-)-ribose), two uronic acids (d-galacturonic acid and d-glucuronic acid) and one aldonic acid (d-gluconic acid)) of lignocellulosic biomass was examined by Catal *et al.* (2008) using air cathode MFCs. Results revealed that bioelectricity was generated from all the substrates tested and the mixed bacterial culture, which was enriched using acetate as a carbon source, adapted well to all the substrates tested, although the adaptation times varied from 1 to 70 h. Furthermore, the maximum power density obtained from the substrates ranged from 1240 ± 10 to $2770 \pm 30 \text{ mW/m}^2$ at current density range of $0.76\text{--}1.18 \text{ mA/cm}^2$. It was also observed that d-Mannose resulted in the lowest maximum power density, whereas d-glucuronic acid generated the highest maximum power density and coulombic efficiency ranged from 21 to 37%. For all the substrates tested, the relationship between the maximum voltage output and the substrate concentration appeared to follow saturation kinetics at 120Ω external resistance. The estimated maximum voltage output ranged between 0.26 and 0.44 V and half-saturation kinetic constants ranged from 111 to 725 mg/L. In terms of COD removal was also found to be over 80% for all the substrates.

Ahmad *et al.* (2013) compared the performances of cellulosic MFCs with respect to the properties of the different cellulosic substrate each utilized. Results revealed that in terms of the mean peak currents and mean peak power densities MFCs run on cellulose were electrically outperformed by those run on starch but not those run on chitin and coulombic efficiency was greatest for soluble polysaccharide substrates, whether starch or cellulose. Coulombic efficiency was also observed to decrease for insoluble polysaccharide substrates, as the degree of polymerization increased. Huang and Logan (2008) examined the effectiveness of simultaneous electricity production and treatment of a paper recycling plant wastewater using MFCs. Results revealed that treatment efficiency was limited by wastewater conductivity. When a 50 mM phosphate buffer solution (PBS, 5.9 mS/cm) was added to the wastewater, power densities reached $501 \pm 20 \text{ mWm}^{-2}$, with a coulombic efficiency of $16 \pm 2\%$. There was efficient removal of soluble organic matter, with $73 \pm 1\%$ removed based on soluble chemical oxygen demand (SCOD) and only slightly greater total removal ($76 \pm 4\%$) based on total COD (TCOD) over a 500-h batch cycle. Cellulose was nearly completely removed ($96 \pm 1\%$) during treatment. Further increasing the conductivity (100 mM PBS) increased power to $672 \pm 27 \text{ mW/m}^2$. In contrast, only $144 \pm 7 \text{ mW/m}^2$ was produced using an unamended wastewater (0.8 mS/cm) with TCOD, SCOD, and cellulose removals of $29 \pm 1\%$, $51 \pm 2\%$, and $16 \pm 1\%$ (350-h batch cycle). These results demonstrate limitations to treatment efficiencies with actual wastewaters caused by solution conductivity compared to laboratory experiments under more optimal conditions.

Recent studies have also demonstrated that stable power could be generated in MFCs using agricultural residues hydrolysate, which is the most abundant component of plant biomass readily available as a waste material in many parts of the world. For instance, Zhang *et al.* (2009) demonstrated that bioelectricity generation from wheat

straw hydrolysates could be achieved in two-chamber MFCs. In their investigations, the authors found that the power density reached 123 mW/m^2 with an initial hydrolysate concentration of $1,000 \text{ mg COD L}^{-1}$, while CEs ranged from 37.1 to 15.5%, corresponding to the initial hydrolysate concentrations of 250 to $2,000 \text{ mg COD/L}$. In 2014, Song *et al.* (2014) investigated the influence of lignocellulosic biomass addition on bioelectricity generation from solid phase MFCs. In their study, The authors used *Acorus calamus* leaves and wheat straw, which were added to a matrix of sediment and soil inside the anode of solid phase microbial fuel cells (SMFCs) in order to increase their output power. Results showed that SMFC containing 3% leaves in their sediment had a maximum power density of 195 mW/m^2 in compared to 4.6 mW/m^2 from that of SMFC without leaves. Similarly, SMFC containing 1% wheat straw in their soil environment had a maximum power density of 167 mW/m^2 . Thus, the addition of biomass in appropriate proportions increases contact opportunities between the matrix, the anode and the added biomass, increases organic matter content, and enhances cellulase activity, thus serving as an important method for enhancing output power in SMFCs. In a related study, Sajana *et al.* (2014), shows that up to 2% addition of cellulose has been reported to improve the performance of sediment microbial fuel cells (SMFCs) in a aquaculture pond sediment.

After cellulose, chitin is the most widespread biopolymer in nature. Enormous amounts of chitin can be found in the biosphere. It can be extracted from three sources, namely crustaceans (crab and shrimp shells), insects (cuticles of insects) and microorganisms (e.g., fungal cell walls and yeast). Fungi provide the largest amount of chitin in the soil (6–12 % of chitin biomass, which is in the range of 500–5000 kg/ha). The main commercial sources of chitin are shells of crustaceans such as shrimps, crabs, lobsters and krill with an estimated annual turnover in the range of 10^{10} - 10^{11} tones making it one of the most abundant biopolymers. Chitin can be readily obtained by simple extraction that involves two steps, demineralization and deproteinisation, which can be conducted by two methods, chemical or biological (Arbia *et al.*, 2013). Chitin can be used as a slowly degrading substrate in MFCs and thus as a long-term fuel to sustain power by these devices in remote locations.

Chitin being one of the most abundant biopolymers in nature and the main composition of shrimp and crab shells (usually as food wastes) has been investigated in recent times as potential feedstock (substrate) for energy recovery. Recently, Li *et al.*, (2017) demonstrated that chitin could be degraded effectively by an electroactive bacterium in MFC, and their findings suggest that MFC bioelectrochemical system might be useful for the degradation of recalcitrant biomass to recover energy. The authors investigated the anaerobic degradation of chitin by *Aeromonas hydrophila*, a chitinolytic and popular electroactive bacterium, in both fermentation and MFC systems. Results revealed that the primary chitin metabolites produced in MFC were succinate, lactate, acetate, formate, and ethanol and the total metabolite concentration from chitin degradation increased seven-fold in MFC compared to the fermentation system, as well as additional electricity generation. Results also showed that *A. hydrophila* degraded GlcNAc (the intermediate of chitin hydrolysis) significantly faster (0.97 and $0.94 \text{ mM C/d/mM-GlcNAc}$) than chitin (0.13 and $0.03 \text{ mM C/d/mM-GlcNAc}$) in MFC and fermentation systems, indicating that extracellular hydrolysis of chitin was the rate-limiting step and this step could be accelerated in MFC.

To increase power generation from marine sediments powered MFCs, Rezaei *et al.* (2007) investigated the effect of three particulate substrates - two commercially available chitin products differing in particle size and biodegradability (Chitin 20 and Chitin 80) and cellulose powder. Results showed that maximum power densities using chitin in substrate-enhanced sediment MFC (SEM) were 76 ± 25 and $84 \pm 10 \text{ mW/m}^2$ (normalized to cathode projected surface area) for Chitin 20 and Chitin 80, respectively, versus less than 2 mW/m^2 for an unamended control. Power generation over a 10-day period averaged $64 \pm 27 \text{ mW/m}^2$ (Chitin 20) and $76 \pm 15 \text{ mW/m}^2$ (Chitin 80). With cellulose, a similar maximum power was initially generated ($83 \pm 3 \text{ mW/m}^2$), but power rapidly decreased after only 20 h. Maximum power densities over the next 5 days varied substantially among replicate cellulose-fed reactors, ranging from 29 ± 12 to $62 \pm 23 \text{ mW/m}^2$. These results suggest that it is possible to increase operation times by controlling particle size, mass, and type of material needed to achieve desired power levels that could theoretically be sustained over periods of years or even decades.

The effects of chitin particle size on PD and length of power cycle (longevity) were examined by Rezaei *et al.* (2009). The authors examined power generation from chitin particles sieved to produce three average particle sizes (0.28, 0.46 and 0.78 mm). Results revealed that the longevity increased from 9 to 33 days with an increase in the particle diameter from 0.28 to 0.78 mm and CE also increased with particle size from 18% to 56%. It was also found that the maximum PD was lower for the largest (0.78 mm) particles (176 mW/m^2), with higher power densities for the 0.28 mm (272 mW/m^2) and 0.46 mm (252 mW/m^2) particle sizes.

3.2.6 Synthetic Wastewater

Moon *et al.* (2006) used artificial wastewater (AW) to analyse the performance of MFC under different conditions using a mediator-less MFC. Results revealed that highest power density of 0.56 W/m^2 was achieved with AW of

300 mg/L fed at the rate of 0.53 mL/min at 35 °C. The power per unit cell working volume was also found to be 102 mW/L.

The simultaneous generation of electricity and removal of organic load from synthetic wastewater containing equimolar concentration of glucose and glutamic acid was investigated by Shankar *et al.* (2015). The authors investigated the effect of initial COD (mg/L), anodic pH and metals (Zn^{2+} , Cr^{6+} , and Fe^{3+}) concentration on the generation of current density and voltage. Findings revealed that although, the amount of COD removed increases with increase in the initial COD value from 500 to 2500 mg/L, the maximum generation of current density (19 mA/m²) and voltage (14.8 mV), after 7 days of operation, was achieved at the initial COD value of 1500 mg/L at anodic pH value of 7. Results further revealed that addition of metals initially increases the voltage and power density generation, attains a maximum value at a certain metal concentration and decreases thereafter with increase in metal concentration. Optimum concentration of metals, that is, 8 mg/L Zn^{2+} , 7 mg/L Cr^{6+} , and 10 mg/L Fe^{3+} in the solution produces maximum voltage of 142, 490, and 321 mV, after 7 days of operation, respectively. Corresponding maximum power densities were 6.9, 508, and 192 mW/m², respectively.

Shankar *et al.* (2015) recently used a membrane less MFC with internal resistance of 4.9 M Ω in continuous mode to investigate the simultaneous generation of electricity and removal of organics from synthetic wastewater with equimolar concentration of glucose and glutamic acid. The authors used activated sludge of a municipal wastewater treatment plant (MW-AS) as the source of mixed microbial strains and graphite sheets as electrodes. The authors examined the effects of process variables such as empty bed contact time, electrode surface area, inter electrode distance, mediator concentration on the voltage generation and COD removal. Findings showed that under optimum conditions with initial COD value of 500 mg/L, the maximum voltage and current have been found to be ~ 200 mV and ~ 2.5 mA, respectively, with the COD removal of 90%.

Using simulated wastewater, Savda and Sreekrishnan (2012) investigated the feasibility of using agar salt bridges for proton transport in MFCs. Similarly, using the same substrate; the authors also elucidated the effect of mediators on electricity production from wastewaters. In order to offset the very high cost of proton exchange membrane, salt bridges have been used in dual chamber MFCs. Results revealed that varying the salt concentration in agar salt bridges from 1% to 10%, changes PD from 1.71 to 84.99 mW/m³ with a concomitant variation in PD from 0.32 to 16.02 mW/m². It was also found that maximum PD was observed at 5% salt concentration with 10% agar, which was accompanied by 88.41% COD reduction. In the case of methylene blue (0.01 mM) as electron mediator, the voltage and current generation were 0.551 V and 0.47 mA, respectively and maximum open circuit voltage of 0.718 V was seen at 0.08 mM methylene blue concentration, whereas maximum power densities of 17.59 mW/m² and 89.22 mW/m³ were obtained. Furthermore, the authors also investigated different concentrations of neutral red. A maximum open circuit voltage of 0.730 V was seen at 0.01mM neutral red, corresponding to a power density of 12.02 mW/m² (volumetric power density of 60.97 mW/m³).

3.2.7 Landfill Leachate

Landfill leachates are heavily polluted landfill effluents with a complex composition containing dissolved organic matter, inorganic macro-components, heavy metals, and xenobiotic organic compounds (Kjeldsen *et al.*, 2002). In 2006, Frew and Christy (2006) investigated the possibility of using landfill leachate as a productive source of substrate and microbes for generating electricity in microbial fuel cells. The authors used multiple fuel cells with landfill leachate in the anodic chamber and a buffer solution of KH_2PO_4 in the cathodic chamber using a proton exchange membrane (NafionTM). Graphite plates were used as the electrodes in both chambers. Findings revealed that microorganisms in landfill leachate are electrochemically active, and thus, landfill leachate can be an effective source of bioelectricity in MFCs. Furthermore, the addition of 10 mL of a 0.4% soluble sugar mixture (0.1% each of glucose, cellobiose, maltose, and xylose) provided enough food source for the microorganisms in the leachate to generate electrical voltage that was nearly three times the amount produced without the sugar mixture (0.120 volts).

The use of landfill leachate for power generation and nitrogen/COD removal has attracted growing research interest in recent times. For instance, Lee *et al.* (2013) designed and tested MFC in terms of power generation and nitrogen removal using landfill leachate with high ammonium content as substrates. The authors used two MFC reactors, an ammonium oxidation/MFC reactor and an MFC/Anammox reactor. Findings revealed that the landfill leachate generated a power density of 8 mWm⁻² and 92% of nitrogen removal. Similarly, for the MFC/Anammox reactor, a power density of 12 mW/m² was achieved with 94% nitrogen removal. Compared with the ammonium oxidation/MFC reactor, 50% more energy was generated because in the MFC/Anammox reactor, nitrite served as the electron acceptor; while in the Ammonium Oxidation/MFC reactor, nitrate served as the electron acceptor. Greenman *et al.* (2009) investigated the performance of leachate strengths in MFC in terms of BOD removal efficiencies and electricity generation, when a fixed resistive load was connected. Results demonstrated that it is possible to generate electricity and simultaneously treat landfill leachate in MFC. Furthermore, electrical output levels and BOD concentrations at the MFC columns showed a linear relationship, which allows the system to be used as a B O D

sensor. However, part of the BOD removal was not associated with power generation and was attributed to the presence of alternative end terminal electron acceptors and volatilization.

Damiano *et al.* (2014) designed and operated an MFC using landfill leachate for waste treatment, while simultaneously producing electricity. Two designs were tested in batch cycles using landfill leachate as a substrate without inoculation (908 to 3,200 mg/L COD): Circle (934 mL) and large-scale MFC (18.3 L). Results revealed that aximum PD of 24 to 31 mW/m² (653 to 824 mW/m³) were achieved using the Circle MFC, and a maximum voltage of 635 mV was produced using the larger-scale MFC. Moreover, in the Circle MFC, COD, BOD, TOC, and ammonia were removed at an average of 16%, 62%, 23%, and 20%, respectively. The larger-scale MFC achieved an average of 74% BOD removal, 27% TOC removal, and 25% ammonia reduction.

Puig *et al.* (2011) assessed the feasibility of using MFCs in landfill leachate treatment and electricity production under high levels of nitrogen concentration (6033 mg N/L) and conductivity (73,588 μ S/cm). Results revealed up to 8.5 kg COD/m³/d of biodegradable organic matter was removed at the same time as electricity (344 mW/m³) was produced.

4. CURRENT CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

Although in recent years advances in MFCs research have shown that power generation from MFCs have improved considerably and also reached the level of primary power target in small lab-scale systems, ever since when scientist discovered that bioelectricity could be generated in MFCs, power output is still a big challenge, which may be attributed to a number of factors such as high internal resistance, nature of the electrode, and substrate. Another important challenge is the high cost of MFCs (Hu, 2008). It is agreed that the power output of most MFCs is too low for any envisioned applications (Lovley, 2008). High cost of precious metal catalyst such as platinum, which is usually needed on cathode, is also a big limiting factor in MFC system.

Operational conditions such as feeding mode, flow rate, temperature, pH, organic loading rate, hydraulic retention time, microbial selection and colonization efficacy, and internal resistance, substrate selection plays an important role in MFCs performance. Optimizing operating conditions is an important approach to improve MFC performance and enhance power output. Besides factors like temperature and pH, biofilms (Jung and Regan, 2007), using Open-air biocathodes (Clauwaert *et al.* (2007), nature of the electrodes (Chang *et al.*, 2016), mixing intensity to improve mass transfer (Pham *et al.*, 2008), using effective, high energy yielding substrate could be an effective method to improve the performance of MFCs. Thus, further research is needed in order to enhance the performance/power outputs of MFCs in all these parameters limiting the performance particularly in substrate selection. High nutrient rich wastewaters have a huge potential as substrates in MFCs. However, the selection of wastewater and its ionic strength are important for achieving maximum power outputs in MFCs for bioelectricity generation and wastewater treatment. There are several ways by which the existing limitations in MFCs could be overcome as described in Pant *et al.* (2010).

5. CONCLUSION

This mini review provides an overview of the various substrates that have been used in MFCs for bioelectricity generation, waste treatment, as well as resource recovery. However, not all the substrates are covered in this paper and newer substrates are brought under these systems with improved outputs both in terms of power generation as well as waste treatment. During the early stage of MFC, conventional (simple carbohydrates) substrates such as glucose, acetate, and lactate and glucose were commonly used, but in recent years researchers are using more unconventional natural and synthetic substrates such as wastewater (domestic, industrial, and swine) for simultaneous generation of bioelectricity and waste treatment as well as improving MFC performance.

MFC technology contains many hurdles before it can be implemented as a form of bioelectricity and wastewater treatment (e.g., cathode material costs, small power output due to anode surface area, and internal resistance issues, and substrate). However, it has been proven to be a worthwhile technological pursuit due to it's proven ability to generate usable renewable energy, waste treatment as well as resource recovery.

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